

EFFECT OF VELOCITY ON THE COMPRESSION BEHAVIOR AND ENERGY ABSORPTION OF THE NOVEL AUXETIC STRUCTURE

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Abstract. This paper proposes a novel two-layered auxetic geometry that is specifically designed for energy absorption application under impact. In the two-layered geometry, the outer-layer was designed to promote auxetic effect and inner layer was provided for reinforcement. Addition middle link was also provided for enhancing the stiffness. The said geometry was designed, fabricated, and tested. An FE model was developed and validated from compression test data. A similar FE model was used to study the effect of impact velocities on the compression behavior of geometry. The results revealed contrast behavior, where geometry offers more resistance to the impact as velocity increases and absorbs more energy. Auxetic effect was also found to be sensitive to the impact velocity. Auxetic effect seemed to play roll in performance by pulling more material in the path of compression eventually offering enhanced resistance to the impact and higher energy absorption.

Keywords: Auxetic material, Smart material, Energy Absorption, Meta-materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Material with negative poisson's ratio (NPR) shows contrast behavior to that of natural materials. They contract when compressed and expand when stretched. History of the NPR materials dated back to 19th century [1] but it was revived in 1987 with synthesis of foam with negative poisson's ratio by Lakes [2]. A formal name was given to NPR by Evan [3] in 1991. Auxetic materials exhibits enhanced mechanical properties [4]. Auxetic effect is achieved when members/struts of the structure deform towards the center of geometry under compression. This behavior offers more resistance to the compression [5]. Many studies have been reported where auxetic structures have been used for energy absorption. Allen et al., [6] studied the feasibility of auxetic foam for sport safety applications and reported better performance of foam at higher impact. Khan et al., [7] reviewed the feasibility of auxetic structure in ballistic applications and reported positive response. Tahir et al., [8] reviewed the applicability of auxetic materials for personal protection and underlined the energy absorption capabilities of auxetic materials. Similarly Shah et al., [9] conducted the FE analysis of auxetic structure for application in ballistic core and reported encouraging results. Imbalzano et al., [10] reported use of auxetic sandwich panels for localized ballistic impact where plastic deformation and densification seemed to play crucial role. Many such similar studies were reported. Presented paper studies the effects of impact velocity on the novel two layered auxetic structures specifically tailored for energy absorbing application.

2 DESIGN, FABRICATION AND TESTING OF AUXETIC GEOMETRY.

2.1 Conceptual Design

Fig. 1. (a) Proposed auxetic structure (b) Fabricated specimen.

The presented geometry is specifically designed to meet requirements like high stiffness, high energy absorption, high auxetic effect, etc. The two-layered geometry is designed symmetrically about x and y axes to avoid uneven stress distribution. The outer layer of the geometry is inverted honeycomb. The struts of the given layer are placed inclined at angle referred as ‘auxetic angle (θ)’ hereinafter. The said auxetic angle is intentionally kept at 80° to keep balance between contribution of buckling and bending in mode of deformation. The inner layer of hexagonal shape is designed to provide reinforcement for geometry. Both the layers were connected by strategically placed members to promote auxetic effect. The middle link MN Fig. 1 (a) is provided to enhance stiffness of the structure. Porosity or empty spaces in the geometry are provided to accommodate inward deformation of the struts to promote auxetic effect.

2.2 Fabrication of the specimen

The three specimens of same kind as one of shown in **Fig. 1.** (b) were fabricated using Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) 3D printing technique. The length (l_0) was kept at 30 mm, thickness (t_0) was 1.2 mm and the depth was kept 15 mm. The Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) thermoplastic polymer was used as a parent material with 100% infill pattern. A standard nozzle of 0.6 mm and layer thickness of 0.2 mm was used. Specimens were 3D printed along z-axis. Specimens were designed in such a way that it did not require any support structures and post-processing.

2.3 Properties of parent material

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. (a) Tensile Specimens and (b) The results of uniaxial tensile testing.

The parent material ABS polymer was characterized by conducting uniaxial tensile testing according to ASTM D638 standards with Universal Testing Machine (UTM). The three ASTM D638 type IV tensile specimens as shown in **Fig. 2.** (a), were fabricated using similar FDM processing by keeping all other attributes the same. The results of the uniaxial tensile tests are given in **Fig. 2.** (b). Average values of the results of tensile tests are given in **Table 1.** Given properties were used to generate customize material card for FE simulation.

Table 1. Properties of parent material used for FE modelling.

Properties	Density	Poisson's Ratio	Young's Modulus	Yield Stress	Ultimate Stress	Failure Strain
	Kg/mm ³		MPa	MPa	MPa	%
Avg. Values	1060	0.4089	700	36	37	6.8

2.4 Uniaxial compression testing of the auxetic specimens

Uniaxial compression tests were conducted on all three specimens to study compression behavior of geometry. ASTM D695 standards were employed for compression testing. The specimen was placed on the fixed platen and speed was given to moving platen as shown in **Fig.**

3. (a). The crosshead speed of the moving platen was kept at 10 mm/min. The compression test was forced to stop when specimen went under out of plane deformation due to undesired fracture in the middle link MN (**Fig. 1.(a)**) as shown in **Fig. 3.(b)**. Results of the uniaxial test data are given in **Fig. 4**.

Fig. 3. (a) Uniaxial compression test setup and (b) Deformed specimens after compression.

3 FE MODELLING AND VALIDATION.

3.1 FE Modelling Setup

Finite element analysis in the field of auxetics is catching a grip due to its potential for accurate and versatile nature [11]. In this study FE modelling was conducted using commercial ANSYS® Workbench Explicit Dynamics software package. Compression testing was simulated with CAD model of two compression plates and a specimen. Like compression test, one plate was assigned a ‘FIXED’ support and other plate was assigned with ‘VELOCITY.’ Both plates were assigned with ‘RIGID’ status. Specimen model was placed between the plates. AUTOMATIC CONTACTS were enabled to reduce computation time. To simulate IMPACT, velocity was assigned from the initial ($time=0$) timestep. Moving platen was assigned with higher velocity of 10 m/s than actual testing velocity to reduce computation time. To make the effect of higher velocity minimal, ‘MAXIMUM ENERGY ERROR’ was kept under the default value of 0.1. A ‘PROGRAMME CONTROLLED’ meshing was employed which turned out to be QUAD element dominant due to simple geometry of the structure. Mesh size was converged at 1.2 mm after convergence study. Stress was measured with ‘NORMAL STRESS PROBE’ in the direction of loading. Lateral deformation was measured with deformation probe in that direction. More than fifteen features like lines, points, faces, etc. were probed to measure lateral deformation for assessing auxetic effect.

3.2 FEM validation

To validate the FE model, Experimental data and test data were matched as shown in **Fig. 4**. It is evident from the data that both Experimental data and test data are showing significant resemblance. Some deviations can be seen in data that could be explained as follows. In the FE modelling middle link MN (**Fig. 1.(a)**) was buckled leaving a stress spike at 0.05 strain whereas in actual testing middle link ruptured at a tri-junction as shown in **Fig. 3. (b)**. Testing curves seem to decline below the experimental curve after 0.05 strain, the behavior could be also attributed to the rupture in the middle link since rupture lowered the stiffness and eventually lowered the performance of the geometry. All the above discussion and data shown in **Fig. 4** validates the FE model, and the same model was used for further analysis.

Fig. 4. Compression test data and FE data with the best fitting curve for FE data.

4 EFFECT OF IMPACT VELOCITY ON THE AUXETIC STRUCTURE.

The effect of impact velocity on the auxetic structure was assessed. A similar FE model was employed for the study. In the said FE model only ‘VELOCITY’ attribute was varied in the step of 10 m/s from 10 m/s to 100 m/s. It is evident from **Fig. 5.** (a) and (b) that compression response of the auxetic structure is sensitive to the impact velocity.

4.1 Compression response to the impact velocity.

Interesting patterns can be observed from Stress-strain curve in **Fig. 5.** (a). A typical stress strain curve for auxetic materials can be divided into three parts viz. peak stress region, plateau region and densification [5]. The magnitude of peak stress and corresponding strain seems to increase with velocity. Peak stress for 10 m/s velocity is around 5 MPa and attained at 0.05 strain whereas for 100 m/s, it was around 45 MPa and attained at 0.1 strain. It is evident that the response of the same structure to different velocities is different. The velocities from 10 m/s to 70 m/s has shown similar stress- strain curve whereas stress-strain curve of velocities above 70 m/s is experienced initial peak feature at 0.016 strain. At low velocities amount of input energy is low which enables the whole structure to follow due course of gradual deformation which is elastic buckling (due to impact) followed by elastic bending which further experiences plastic deformation i.e. visible in **Fig. 7** where at 10 m/s velocity and 0.1 strain, all struts underwent deformation unlike at 100 m/s. The relative smoothness of the stress-strain curve also can be attributed to the gradual deformation.

At higher velocities, a high amount of energy enters the system in a very short time due to impact. Higher energy input causes struts near impact location to undergo sudden plastic deformation without following the deformation sequence. Instantaneous plastic deformation absorbs the impact and offers higher resistance to compression which is reflected as peak stress. Plastic deformation of struts near impact allows delayed deformation of struts far from impact location as shown in **Fig. 7**. More peak features are becoming visible at higher velocities since different layers of structure are offering different stiffness and hence the resistance to plastic deformation. Velocity does not seem to be an influencing factor in densification.

4.2 Auxetic behavior of the structure at different velocities.

It is visible from **Fig. 5.** (b) that poisson’s ratio is also sensitive to the velocity. A trend can be seen in the poisson’s ratio where the lowest poisson’s ratio (-1.37) can be seen at 10 m/s and highest (-

0.637) can be seen at 100 m/s. Poisson’s ratio increases as velocity increases. This behavior again can be attributed to the deformation mode. At lower velocities structure followed sequence of gradual deformation which allows struts to deform inwards in elastic region attaining the least poisson’s ratio. But as velocity increases, plastic deformation of the struts adversely affects the auxetic effect. As velocity increases, the strain corresponding to least poisson’s ratio also increases due to the same abovementioned reason.

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Fig. 5. (a) Stress-strain curve and (b) Poisson’s Ratio for different impact velocities

5 ENERGY ABSORPTION OF THE AUXETIC GEOMETRY.

Energy absorption of the geometry was assessed by measuring the area under the stress-strain curve till densification strain. MATLAB® software package was employed for measuring energy absorption. An exponential growth pattern can be seen in energy absorption as velocity increases. The presence of the middle link seems beneficial at high velocities. It could be said that energy absorption increases with velocity. Expedited plastic deformation under high velocity seemed to be beneficial for energy absorption.

Fig. 6. Specific Energy absorption (J/g) for different velocities.

Fig. 7. Deformation of auxetic geometry at different velocities (True scale 1.0).

6 CONCLUSION

The auxetic structure has shown better results in its class. Rough conclusions can be drawn as follows. Compression behavior and poisson's ratio of auxetic geometry is sensitive to velocity. Also, mode of deformations varies with velocity. As velocity increases resistance from geometry also increases due to expedited plastic deformation and it hampers auxetic behavior. Specific energy absorption increases with velocity. Given geometry has proven its potential to replace conventional energy absorption materials and can be used in several applications like sensors, ballistic armors etc.

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